
PILE: Policy Improvement Through Evolving LLM Generated Code

Alex Havrilla
Department of Mathematics
Georgia Tech
Atlanta, GA, 30308
ahavrilla3@gatech.edu

Chris Cui
Affiliation
Address
Email

Abstract

The deep reinforcement learning (**DRL**) approach to policy learning parameterizes the learned policy with a neural network. Policy improvement can then be implemented through a number of gradient based approaches. Programmatic reinforcement learning (**PRL**) offers a more interpretable alternative to this paradigm, representing policies as DSL programs. However, PRL methods are extremely sample inefficient, often requiring millions of policy iterations in practice. To address this sample inefficiency, we instead propose to represent policies in generic python code and apply an LLM-driven evolutionary search procedure as the policy improvement operator. As part of this process we propose the use of *self-metrics*, LLM-generated python functions taking as input policy rollout data and producing measurements of policy behavior, as a means of implementing feedback driven *policy refinement*. Our complete method **PILE** combines this LLM-driven policy evolution procedure with policy improvement through self-metric refinement. We evaluate **PILE** on Mini-grid environments, finding **PILE** significantly improves over best-of-n LLM policy sampling with less than a thousand policy iterations.

1 Introduction

Given a Markov decision process (**MDP**) (S, A, P_a, R_a) , the goal of reinforcement learning is to learn a policy $\pi^* : S \rightarrow A$ maximizing the return $G_T = \sum_{i=1}^T \gamma^i R_i$ where R_i is the reward received by π at the i th time-step and $0 < \gamma \leq 1$ is an optional discount factor. Let $\Pi = \{\pi : S \rightarrow A\}$ represent the space of policies. Given an initial policy π_0 , a *policy improvement operator* $I : \Pi \rightarrow \Pi$ can be applied to find a new policy π_1 which achieves better return G_T compared π_0 . For simple environments with limited state and action spaces, the policy π can be parameterized as a correspondingly simple “look-up” table mapping states to actions. The policy improvement operation can be formulated as a dynamic programming problem [Agarwal et al., 2021]. In practical settings, both action and state spaces become too large to take this simplified approach. Instead, deep reinforcement learning (**DRL**) uses deep neural networks to parameterize the policy π and a new family of gradient-based techniques to implement neural network policy improvement. However, the resulting neural policies are uninterpretable, making them difficult to use in many practical situations.

In this paper, we explore policies represented as Large Language Model (**LLM**) generated python code. To implement policy improvement we combine an evolutionary search procedure in function space [Romera-Paredes et al., 2024] with mutations produced by LLMs. We combine two types of structured mutation in the evolutionary process. The first type utilizes a low-cost *policy designer* to generate new code policies conditioned on high-return existing policies. The second type utilizes a more expensive *policy analyzer* to write *policy self-metrics* which generate feedback on how the current policy is behaving. This feedback is then used to intelligently *refine* the policy to resolve

Figure 1: Diagram of each PILE iteration. First sample a policy for mutation. Then either apply the policy designer to conditionally generate a new policy or the policy analyzer to observe policy failure modes and perform policy refinement. Finally, evaluate the new policy in the environment and add it to the policy archive.

existing failure modes. For example, a useful self-metric might measure the number of times a policy attempts to pick up an object while the agent’s inventory is full. Often, the data from self-metrics can then be used to identify failure modes of the current policy, better directing the mutation of the policy designer. The policy designer and policy analyzer are combined in the same evolutionary process with the cheap policy designer being called the majority of the time and the expensive policy analyzer being called less-often to resolve otherwise difficult to overcome policy failure modes.

In summary, we make the following contributions

- Evolving RL code policies via LLMs as prompted mutation operators.
- The introduction of *policy self-metrics* allowing efficient observation and refinement of existing policies.
- An ablation of PILE’s components to understand the proposed method’s strengths and weaknesses.

Related work Programmatic reinforcement learning [Verma et al., 2019b,a, Qiu and Zhu, 2022] was introduced as a method of improving the interpretability of black-box neural policies. Sometimes a neural policy is first learned [Verma et al., 2019b] and then evolutionary/local search is run to find a program approximating the oracle neural policy. Very recently Liu et al. [2024] proposed to accelerate the local search with an LLM proposing a set of initial program candidates. They found this resulted in improved sample efficiency when compared to other local search driven PRL baselines.

LLMs have also been recently used to act as black box optimizers [Yang et al., 2024] for a variety of tasks. Hemberg et al. [2024] applies LLMs to evolve code to solve various software tasks. Fernando et al. [2023], Guo et al. [2024] evolve new prompts to improve LLM output. Romera-Paredes et al. [2024] evolves heuristics used to construct counterexamples in combinatorial mathematics. Also closely related is a recent line of work using LLMs to write programmatic reward functions [Ma et al., 2024] and even whole environments [Faldor et al., 2024].

2 PILE: Policy Improvement through Evolving LLM Generated Code

Given a MDP (S, A, P_a, R_a) our goal is to produce a policy $\pi : A \rightarrow S$ maximizing the return coming from R_a . To implement PILE, we parameterize S, A as python objects which can be used

to define the python function type `policy(s: S) -> A` which implements a policy π as a python function. We additionally generate abstract textual descriptions of the state space and action space, $str(S)$, $str(A)$, which are used in LLM prompts.

PILE adopts the same evolutionary strategy utilized by FunSearch [Romera-Paredes et al., 2024]. The algorithm begins by initializing a set of N *islands* housing independently evolving policy populations. Maintaining parallel islands partially addresses the tendency of evolutionary methods to converge to local optima at the cost of additional sampling. Additionally, after every `num_reset_steps`, the bottom worst performing islands are emptied and repopulated with samples from the top half of islands to avoid wasting samples on poorly performing policies. Once the islands are initialized, policy generation and mutation is done using two complementary approaches:

Generating New Policies via the Policy Designer Given a description of the state, action space, and goal, the *policy designer* begins by independently and unconditionally sampling a set of seed policies which are used to populate the islands. Each policy’s fitness is evaluated as the average return achieved by the policy after rolling it out R many times in the environment. After `num_seed` seed steps, each subsequent round uniformly randomly samples an island and then samples a policy on the island with higher fitness policies being given higher probability of selection. The policy designer is then prompted to generate a new policy by mutating the selected policy. The new policy’s fitness is evaluated and added to the population of the selected island.

Refining New Policies via Self-Metric Feedback with the Policy Analyzer Often evolutionary methods will easily “get-stuck” in local optima after many rounds of evolution. This is especially apparent in our setting where sparse reward bottlenecks in the environment often limit further improvement. To address this difficulty, we introduce **self-metric guided policy refinement** as a method of detecting and analyzing policy failure modes. This process begins by randomly sampling an island and then selecting the highest fitness policy on the island for policy analysis. A pre-defined set of 3-4 basic metrics are then applied to the policy, generating observational policy data. Each metric is a python function which takes in policy rollout data in the form of (s, a, r) trajectory tuples and returns a dictionary of floats containing different measurements of policy behavior (e.g. the number of times the policy attempted to open a door). The *policy analyzer* is then prompted to generate a hypothesis about the current policy’s behavior conditioned on the policy source code and metric observations. To confirm this hypothesis, the policy is prompted to propose a new *self-metric*. If the policy analyzer decides the result of the self-metric confirms its hypothesis, it is updated to *refine* the policy to fix/improve the identified failure mode. Further, if the refined policy successfully improves over the fitness of the sampled policy, the new self-metric is saved in a *metric archive* which gets applied to future policies during the first round of analysis. If the policy analyzer is unable to confirm the hypothesis, it is prompted to propose another self-metric to either confirm the hypothesis or generate a new hypothesis. This loop is run a maximum of three times, after which the policy analyzer must unconditionally refine the policy.

At each iteration of the evolutionary loop we sample the policy designer with probability p and the policy analyzer with probability $1 - p$. In practice we implement the policy designer using a weak, fast to sample LLM and the policy analyzer using a strong, slow/expensive to sample LLM. Figure 1 outlines one iteration of the PILE evolutionary process. All LLM prompts can be found in appendix Section A.

3 Experiments

We evaluate PILE in the Dynamic Obstacle and Unlock Pickup Minigrid environments [Chevalier-Boisvert et al., 2023]. A reward of 0.2 is provided for both intermediate goals in Unlock Pickup with 0.6 reward additionally being given for reaching the final goal. The default sparse reward is given for Dynamic Obstacle. To evaluate each policy we sample 20 rollouts with at most $T = 300$ steps each and compute the mean return. We initialize PILE with $N = 5$ islands and $p = 0.75$ probability of mutating with the policy designer. We select a quantized version of Llama-3 70B [Dubey et al., 2024] as the policy designer and implement the policy analyzer using Claude-3.5-Sonnet. After running each method 10 times we plot the mean of the return of the best policy produced by each method. Results are reported in Figure 2.

PILE outperforms IID sampling Results on minigrid show PILE both with and without the policy analyzer outperforms IID policy sampling of the policy designer base LLM by up to 0.2 and 0.1 return

Figure 2: Results on Dynamic Obstacle and Unlock Pickup Minigrid environments. Both PILE and PILE without the policy analyzer improve over the IID sampling (best-of-n) baseline. Incorporating the policy analyzer further improves over sampling with just the policy designer.

respectively. Adding the policy analyzer further improves over utilizing only the policy designer by an additional 0.1 return, demonstrating its effectiveness. Further, both methods are sample efficient, requiring less than a thousand policy iterations to find performant policies. In some cases, policies produced by PILE are even able to solve the entire task despite sparse rewards.

The policy analyzer helps with reward bottlenecks The policy analyzer was introduced to help with locally optimal policies that are difficult to improve on due to sparse rewards in the environment. An analysis of the programs generated by PILE reveals it is reasonably successful at this. The policy analyzer is able to identify several key bottlenecks (such as blocking the door with the key) allowing some policies to successfully complete the final goal. In some cases this is accomplished directly by the refined policy produced by the analyzer and in other cases by subsequent evolutions of the refined policy. Further, both IID and PILE without the analyzer are never produce policies which are able to complete the final goal.

Self-metrics can be unreliable While the policy analyzer can sometimes correctly identify policy failure modes, it can run into trouble writing reliably correct self-metrics. Incorrectly implementing metrics can lead the analyzer to the wrong conclusion, leading to poor refinements. Worse, sometimes a low-quality self-metric by chance leads to an improved policy, resulting in the low-quality metric being added to the metric archive and polluting down-stream analysis.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

We proposed PILE as an evolutionary approach to RL with mutation driven by LLMs and self-metric feedback. Our dual policy designer/policy analyzer strategy allows us to efficiently generate new policies while utilizing feedback from self-metrics written by the policy analyzer. This allows PILE to overcome sparse reward bottlenecks that would otherwise require orders of magnitude more evolutionary steps to solve. However, despite the success of our method, we still suffer from several limitations. The policy analyzer can sometimes produce incorrect self-metrics, polluting policy refinement. Further, in general programmatic representations of the environment struggle to acquire environmental world knowledge, making it difficult to learn low-level environmental details such as “the agent cannot move through dropped keys”. Addressing these difficulties are critical for the future development of LLM-driven policy improvement strategies.

References

Alekh Agarwal, Nan Jiang, Sham M. Kakade, and Wen Sun. *Reinforcement Learning: Theory and Algorithms*. 2021. URL <https://rltheorybook.github.io/>.

Maxime Chevalier-Boisvert, Bolun Dai, Mark Towers, Rodrigo Perez-Vicente, Lucas Willems, Salem Lahlou, Suman Pal, Pablo Samuel Castro, and Jordan Terry. Minigrid & miniworld: Modular &

customizable reinforcement learning environments for goal-oriented tasks. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 36, New Orleans, LA, USA, December 2023*.

Abhimanyu Dubey, Abhinav Jauhri, Abhinav Pandey, Abhishek Kadian, Ahmad Al-Dahle, Aiesha Letman, Akhil Mathur, Alan Schelten, Amy Yang, Angela Fan, Anirudh Goyal, Anthony Hartshorn, Aobo Yang, Archi Mitra, Archie Sravankumar, Artem Korenev, Arthur Hinsvark, Arun Rao, Aston Zhang, Aurelien Rodriguez, Austen Gregerson, Ava Spataru, Baptiste Roziere, Bethany Biron, Binh Tang, Bobbie Chern, Charlotte Caucheteux, Chaya Nayak, Chloe Bi, Chris Marra, Chris McConnell, Christian Keller, Christophe Touret, Chunyang Wu, Corinne Wong, Cristian Canton Ferrer, Cyrus Nikolaidis, Damien Allonsius, Daniel Song, Danielle Pintz, Danny Livshits, David Esiobu, Dhruv Choudhary, Dhruv Mahajan, Diego Garcia-Olano, Diego Perino, Dieuwke Hupkes, Egor Lakomkin, Ehab AlBadawy, Elina Lobanova, Emily Dinan, Eric Michael Smith, Filip Radenovic, Frank Zhang, Gabriel Synnaeve, Gabrielle Lee, Georgia Lewis Anderson, Graeme Nail, Gregoire Mialon, Guan Pang, Guillem Cucurell, Hailey Nguyen, Hannah Korevaar, Hu Xu, Hugo Touvron, Iliyan Zarov, Imanol Arrieta Ibarra, Isabel Kloumann, Ishan Misra, Ivan Evtimov, Jade Copet, Jaewon Lee, Jan Geffert, Jana Vranes, Jason Park, Jay Mahadeokar, Jeet Shah, Jelmer van der Linde, Jennifer Billock, Jenny Hong, Jenya Lee, Jeremy Fu, Jianfeng Chi, Jianyu Huang, Jiawen Liu, Jie Wang, Jiecao Yu, Joanna Bitton, Joe Spisak, Jongsoo Park, Joseph Rocca, Joshua Johnstun, Joshua Saxe, Junteng Jia, Kalyan Vasuden Alwala, Kartikeya Upasani, Kate Plawiak, Ke Li, Kenneth Heafield, Kevin Stone, Khalid El-Arini, Krithika Iyer, Kshitiz Malik, Kuenley Chiu, Kunal Bhalla, Lauren Rantala-Yearly, Laurens van der Maaten, Lawrence Chen, Liang Tan, Liz Jenkins, Louis Martin, Lovish Madaan, Lubo Malo, Lukas Blecher, Lukas Landzaat, Luke de Oliveira, Madeline Muzzi, Mahesh Pasupuleti, Mannat Singh, Manohar Paluri, Marcin Kardas, Mathew Oldham, Mathieu Rita, Maya Pavlova, Melanie Kambadur, Mike Lewis, Min Si, Mitesh Kumar Singh, Mona Hassan, Naman Goyal, Narjes Torabi, Narjey Torabi, Nikolay Bashlykov, Nikolay Bogoychev, Niladri Chatterji, Olivier Duchenne, Onur Çelebi, Patrick Alrassy, Pengchuan Zhang, Pengwei Li, Petar Vasic, Peter Weng, Prajjwal Bhargava, Pratik Dubal, Praveen Krishnan, Punit Singh Koura, Puxin Xu, Qing He, Qingxiao Dong, Ragavan Srinivasan, Raj Ganapathy, Ramon Calderer, Ricardo Silveira Cabral, Robert Stojnic, Roberta Raileanu, Rohit Girdhar, Rohit Patel, Romain Sauvestre, Ronnie Polidoro, Roshan Sumbaly, Ross Taylor, Ruan Silva, Rui Hou, Rui Wang, Saghar Hosseini, Sahana Chennabasappa, Sanjay Singh, Sean Bell, Seohyun Sonia Kim, Sergey Edunov, Shaoliang Nie, Sharan Narang, Sharath Raparthi, Sheng Shen, Shengye Wan, Shruti Bhosale, Shun Zhang, Simon Vandenhende, Soumya Batra, Spencer Whitman, Sten Sootla, Stephane Collot, Suchin Gururangan, Sydney Borodinsky, Tamar Herman, Tara Fowler, Tarek Sheasha, Thomas Georgiou, Thomas Scialom, Tobias Speckbacher, Todor Mihaylov, Tong Xiao, Ujjwal Karn, Vedanuj Goswami, Vibhor Gupta, Vignesh Ramanathan, Viktor Kerkez, Vincent Gonguet, Virginie Do, Vish Vogeti, Vladan Petrovic, Weiwei Chu, Wenhan Xiong, Wenyin Fu, Whitney Meers, Xavier Martinet, Xiaodong Wang, Xiaoqing Ellen Tan, Xinfeng Xie, Xuchao Jia, Xuewei Wang, Yaelle Goldschlag, Yashesh Gaur, Yasmine Babaei, Yi Wen, Yiwen Song, Yuchen Zhang, Yue Li, Yuning Mao, Zacharie Delpierre Coudert, Zheng Yan, Zhengxing Chen, Zoe Papakipos, Aaditya Singh, Aaron Grattafiori, Abha Jain, Adam Kelsey, Adam Shajnfeld, Adithya Gangidi, Adolfo Victoria, Ahuva Goldstand, Ajay Menon, Ajay Sharma, Alex Boesenberg, Alex Vaughan, Alexei Baevski, Allie Feinstein, Amanda Kallet, Amit Sangani, Anam Yunus, Andrei Lupu, Andres Alvarado, Andrew Caples, Andrew Gu, Andrew Ho, Andrew Poulton, Andrew Ryan, Ankit Ramchandani, Annie Franco, Aparajita Saraf, Arkabandhu Chowdhury, Ashley Gabriel, Ashwin Bharambe, Assaf Eisenman, Azadeh Yazdan, Beau James, Ben Maurer, Benjamin Leonhardi, Bernie Huang, Beth Loyd, Beto De Paola, Bhargavi Paranjape, Bing Liu, Bo Wu, Boyu Ni, Braden Hancock, Bram Wasti, Brandon Spence, Brani Stojkovic, Brian Gamido, Britt Montalvo, Carl Parker, Carly Burton, Catalina Mejia, Changan Wang, Changkyu Kim, Chao Zhou, Chester Hu, Ching-Hsiang Chu, Chris Cai, Chris Tindal, Christoph Feichtenhofer, Damon Civin, Dana Beaty, Daniel Kreymer, Daniel Li, Danny Wyatt, David Adkins, David Xu, Davide Testuggine, Delia David, Devi Parikh, Diana Liskovich, Didem Foss, Dingkan Wang, Duc Le, Dustin Holland, Edward Dowling, Eissa Jamil, Elaine Montgomery, Eleonora Presani, Emily Hahn, Emily Wood, Erik Brinkman, Esteban Arcaute, Evan Dunbar, Evan Smothers, Fei Sun, Felix Kreuk, Feng Tian, Firat Ozgenel, Francesco Caggioni, Francisco Guzmán, Frank Kanayet, Frank Seide, Gabriela Medina Florez, Gabriella Schwarz, Gada Badeer, Georgia Swee, Gil Halpern, Govind Thattai, Grant Herman, Grigory Sizov, Guangyi, Zhang, Guna Lakshminarayanan, Hamid Shojanazeri, Han Zou, Hannah Wang, Hanwen Zha, Haroun Habeeb, Harrison Rudolph, Helen Suk, Henry Aspegren, Hunter Goldman, Ibrahim Damlaj, Igor Molybog, Igor Tufanov, Irina-

Elena Veliche, Itai Gat, Jake Weissman, James Geboski, James Kohli, Japhet Asher, Jean-Baptiste Gaya, Jeff Marcus, Jeff Tang, Jennifer Chan, Jenny Zhen, Jeremy Reizenstein, Jeremy Teboul, Jessica Zhong, Jian Jin, Jingyi Yang, Joe Cummings, Jon Carvill, Jon Shepard, Jonathan McPhie, Jonathan Torres, Josh Ginsburg, Junjie Wang, Kai Wu, Kam Hou U, Karan Saxena, Karthik Prasad, Kartikay Khandelwal, Katayoun Zand, Kathy Matosich, Kaushik Veeraraghavan, Kelly Michelena, Keqian Li, Kun Huang, Kunal Chawla, Kushal Lakhota, Kyle Huang, Lailin Chen, Lakshya Garg, Lavender A, Leandro Silva, Lee Bell, Lei Zhang, Liangpeng Guo, Licheng Yu, Liron Moshkovich, Luca Wehrstedt, Madian Khabisa, Manav Avalani, Manish Bhatt, Maria Tsimpoukelli, Martynas Mankus, Matan Hasson, Matthew Lennie, Matthias Reso, Maxim Groshev, Maxim Naumov, Maya Lathi, Meghan Keneally, Michael L. Seltzer, Michal Valko, Michelle Restrepo, Mihir Patel, Mik Vyatskov, Mikayel Samvelyan, Mike Clark, Mike Macey, Mike Wang, Miquel Jubert Hermoso, Mo Metanat, Mohammad Rastegari, Munish Bansal, Nandhini Santhanam, Natascha Parks, Natasha White, Navyata Bawa, Nayan Singhal, Nick Egebo, Nicolas Usunier, Nikolay Pavlovich Laptev, Ning Dong, Ning Zhang, Norman Cheng, Oleg Chernoguz, Olivia Hart, Omkar Salpekar, Ozlem Kalinli, Parkin Kent, Parth Parekh, Paul Saab, Pavan Balaji, Pedro Rittner, Philip Bontrager, Pierre Roux, Piotr Dollar, Polina Zvyagina, Prashant Ratanchandani, Pritish Yuvraj, Qian Liang, Rachad Alao, Rachel Rodriguez, Rafi Ayub, Raghotham Murthy, Raghu Nayani, Rahul Mitra, Raymond Li, Rebekkah Hogan, Robin Battey, Rocky Wang, Rohan Maheswari, Russ Howes, Ruty Rinott, Sai Jayesh Bondu, Samyak Datta, Sara Chugh, Sara Hunt, Sargun Dhillon, Sasha Sidorov, Satadru Pan, Saurabh Verma, Seiji Yamamoto, Sharadh Ramaswamy, Shaun Lindsay, Shaun Lindsay, Sheng Feng, Shenghao Lin, Shengxin Cindy Zha, Shiva Shankar, Shuqiang Zhang, Shuqiang Zhang, Sinong Wang, Sneha Agarwal, Soji Sajuyigbe, Soumith Chintala, Stephanie Max, Stephen Chen, Steve Kehoe, Steve Satterfield, Sudarshan Govindaprasad, Sumit Gupta, Sungmin Cho, Sunny Virk, Suraj Subramanian, Sy Choudhury, Sydney Goldman, Tal Remez, Tamar Glaser, Tamara Best, Thilo Kohler, Thomas Robinson, Tianhe Li, Tianjun Zhang, Tim Matthews, Timothy Chou, Tzook Shaked, Varun Vontimitta, Victoria Ajayi, Victoria Montanez, Vijai Mohan, Vinay Satish Kumar, Vishal Mangla, Vitor Albiero, Vlad Ionescu, Vlad Poenaru, Vlad Tiberiu Mihalescu, Vladimir Ivanov, Wei Li, Wenchen Wang, Wenwen Jiang, Wes Bouaziz, Will Constable, Xiaocheng Tang, Xiaofang Wang, Xiaoqian Wu, Xiaolan Wang, Xide Xia, Xilun Wu, Xinbo Gao, Yanjun Chen, Ye Hu, Ye Jia, Ye Qi, Yenda Li, Yilin Zhang, Ying Zhang, Yossi Adi, Youngjin Nam, Yu, Wang, Yuchen Hao, Yundi Qian, Yuzi He, Zach Rait, Zachary DeVito, Zef Rosnbrick, Zhaoduo Wen, Zhenyu Yang, and Zhiwei Zhao. The llama 3 herd of models, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.21783>.

Maxence Faldor, Jenny Zhang, Antoine Cully, and Jeff Clune. Omni-epic: Open-endedness via models of human notions of interestingness with environments programmed in code, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.15568>.

Chrisantha Fernando, Dylan Banarse, Henryk Michalewski, Simon Osindero, and Tim Rocktäschel. Promptbreeder: Self-referential self-improvement via prompt evolution, 2023. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.16797>.

Qingyan Guo, Rui Wang, Junliang Guo, Bei Li, Kaitao Song, Xu Tan, Guoqing Liu, Jiang Bian, and Yujiu Yang. Connecting large language models with evolutionary algorithms yields powerful prompt optimizers, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.08532>.

Erik Hemberg, Stephen Moskal, and Una-May O’Reilly. Evolving code with a large language model, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.07102>.

Max Liu, Chan-Hung Yu, Wei-Hsu Lee, Cheng-Wei Hung, Yen-Chun Chen, and Shao-Hua Sun. Synthesizing programmatic reinforcement learning policies with large language model guided search, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.16450>.

Yecheng Jason Ma, William Liang, Guanzhi Wang, De-An Huang, Osbert Bastani, Dinesh Jayaraman, Yuke Zhu, Linxi Fan, and Anima Anandkumar. Eureka: Human-level reward design via coding large language models, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.12931>.

Wenjie Qiu and He Zhu. Programmatic reinforcement learning without oracles. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2022. URL <https://openreview.net/forum?id=6Tk2noBdvxt>.

- Bernardino Romera-Paredes, Mohammadamin Barekatin, Alexander Novikov, Matej Balog, M. Pawan Kumar, Emilien Dupont, Francisco J. R. Ruiz, Jordan S. Ellenberg, Pengming Wang, Omar Fawzi, Pushmeet Kohli, and Alhussein Fawzi. Mathematical discoveries from program search with large language models. *Nature*, 625(7995):468–475, 2024. ISSN 1476-4687. doi: 10.1038/s41586-023-06924-6. URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06924-6>.
- Abhinav Verma, Hoang Le, Yisong Yue, and Swarat Chaudhuri. Imitation-projected programmatic reinforcement learning. In H. Wallach, H. Larochelle, A. Beygelzimer, F. d'Alché-Buc, E. Fox, and R. Garnett, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 32. Curran Associates, Inc., 2019a. URL https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2019/file/5a44a53b7d26bb1e54c05222f186dcfb-Paper.pdf.
- Abhinav Verma, Vijayaraghavan Murali, Rishabh Singh, Pushmeet Kohli, and Swarat Chaudhuri. Programmatically interpretable reinforcement learning, 2019b. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1804.02477>.
- Chengrun Yang, Xuezhi Wang, Yifeng Lu, Hanxiao Liu, Quoc V. Le, Denny Zhou, and Xinyun Chen. Large language models as optimizers, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.03409>.

A Prompts

Env Description

Task: {task_description}
The observation space is defined formally as:
{observation_description}
The action space is defined formally as:
{action_description}
Reward description:
{reward_description}

Task Description

You are responsible for designing a decision policy to solve an RL task. You will write a python 'Policy()', which should be initializable without any parameters from the user, object which has two methods:

- 'def act(observation)' which takes in an observation and returns an action.
- 'update(observation, action, reward, next_observation)' which takes in the current observation, chosen action, reward, and next_observation and updates any persistent memory/state between observations. You should never assume the actions you take. 'update' is a good place to test your understanding of the world and record the results.

Note: You should not assume any exploration outside of what is learned during the agent's single rollout in the environment. This means you should not rely on Q-learning, etc. You are allowed to use any python library you want but should not assume access to any other external resources (such as models with downloadable weights) unless otherwise specified.

{env_description}

Designer Prompt

{task_description}
Example Policy:
{policy}
Now write your own policy in a python codeblock.

Initial Analysis Prompt

You are responsible for critiquing a decision policy to solve the following task:
{env_description}
Here is an example policy:
{policy}
The above policy has been rolled out in the environment and a dataset of trajectories has been collected. You must now analyze this dataset to better understand the policy's behavior and environment dynamics. This is done by using reporting functions which capture parts of the policy's behavior and the environmental dynamics.
Report:
{report_results}
Based on this report form ONE specific, concrete hypothesis about how the policy may be failing.
Enclose this hypothesis within the tags <hypothesis>...</hypothesis>
If you feel absolutely confident the hypothesis is confirmed by the existing report print CONFIRMED.
Then write a specific, concise critique enclosed in <critique>...</critique> tags explaining what is wrong and a specific, concrete strategy for how it might fixed.
If you are not confident then do not write a critique and print UNCERTAIN.

Propose Metric Prompt

You are responsible for critiquing a decision policy to solve the following task:

{env_description}

Here is an example policy:

{policy}

The above policy has been rolled out in the environment and a dataset of trajectories has been collected. You must now analyze this dataset to better understand the policy's behavior and environment dynamics. This is done by using reporting functions which capture parts of the policy's behavior and the environmental dynamics. Note: $\text{len}(\text{trajectory}["\text{observations}"]) == \text{len}(\text{trajectory}["\text{actions}"]) + 1$ because the observation after the last action is also saved.

You generated the following hypothesis:

{hypothesis}

To test your hypothesis you must use a report function which aggregates information about policy rollouts in the environment to better understand policy behavior and environmental dynamics. To do so you must design your own report function.

New report functions are of form "REPORT_NAME(observation, action, next_observation, memory: dict) -> dict.

observation: observation at current timestep
action: policy's action after seeing observation
next_observation: observation of state after taking action
memory: dict, a persistent object passed between calls to "REPORT_NAME" over a single trajectory. Can be used to store information for report computation over multiple timesteps. memory["final_step"] = False until the end of the trajectory at which point it is True. Each report should include a "description" variable describing the report. After the final time-step of the trajectory memory["result"]: Union[float, dict[str, float]] should either contain the final result of the report for the trajectory or a dictionary of final results for sub-statistics
memory["description"]: str should contain a detailed description of the report. "REPORT_NAME" should return the memory dict. The report across all trajectories is computed by taking the mean for each trajectory. The report should be contained in a single code block.

Advice for designing good reports:

You should never assume an action results in the expected environmental change. Instead you should use observation and next_observation to check what change (if any) the action produced. If you are reporting a ratio of two numbers you should also report the numerator and denominator.

Analysis Prompt

You are responsible for critiquing a decision policy to solve the following task: {env_description} Here is an example policy: {policy} The above policy has been rolled out in the environment and a dataset of trajectories has been collected. You must now analyze this dataset to better understand the policy's behavior and environment dynamics. This is done by using reporting functions which capture parts of the policy's behavior and the environmental dynamics. You have formed the following hypothesis: {hypothesis} To test this hypothesis you have evaluated the policy using the following report: {report_results} If you feel absolutely confident the hypothesis is confirmed by the existing report print CONFIRMED. Then write a specific, concise critique enclosed in <critique>...</critique> tags explaining what is wrong and a specific, concrete strategy for how it might fixed. If you feel the hypothesis may still be correct but needs more testing then print UNCERTAIN. If the report refutes the hypothesis print REFUTED. Then generate a new concrete, specific hypothesis based on the existing reports. Enclose this hypothesis within the gats <hypothesis>...</hypothesis>

B Policy as Code Examples

Example Code Policy

```
1 import numpy as np
2
3 class Policy:
4     def __init__(self):
5         self.memory = {
6             "key_picked_up": False,
7             "door_opened": False,
8             "door_opening": False,
9             "door_unlocked": False,
10            "box_picked_up": False,
11        } # Persistent memory/state
12        self.steps = 0
13        # Possible actions
14        self.actions = [0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5]
15        # Count for exploration actions
16        self.explore_count = 0
17        # To keep track of tiles explored
18        self.explored_tiles = set()
19
20    def act(self, observation):
21        direction = observation["agent"]["direction"]
22        image = observation["agent"]["image"]
23        inv = observation["inv"]
24        # Current tile agent is standing on
25        current_tile = image[3][6]
26        # Tile agent is facing
27        forward_tile = image[3][5]
28        if forward_tile[0] == 5 and 3 not in inv:
29            # Pickup key
30            return 3
31        if (
32            forward_tile[0] == 4
33            and forward_tile[2] == 2
34            and 5 in inv
35            and not self.memory["door_opening"]
36        ):
37            # Toggle key to open door
38            return 5
39        if forward_tile[0] == 7 and 0 in inv:
40            # Pickup box if available
41            return 3
42        if forward_tile[0] not in [2, 9] and \
43            tuple(forward_tile) not in self.explored_tiles:
44            # Add the tile to explored set
45            self.explored_tiles.add(tuple(forward_tile))
46            # Move forward if facing an unexplored tile
47            return 2
48        # Exploration strategy
49        self.explore_count += 1
50        if self.explore_count % 3 == 0:
51            return np.random.choice([0, 1])
52        # Randomly turn left or right every 3rd step
53        if self.explore_count % 2 == 0:
54            return 2 # Move forward every 2nd step
55        return 2 # Move forward by default
```

Example Code Policy Continued.

```
1 def update(self, observation, \
2 action, reward, next_observation):
3     self.steps += 1
4
5     if not key_picked_up and reward == 0.2:
6         self.memory["key_picked_up"] = True
7     if not door_unlocked and reward == 0.2:
8         self.memory["door_unlocked"] = True
```

Example Self-Metric.

```
1 def report_inventory_management(observation, action,
2 next_observation, memory):
3     if 'inventory_full_when_box_seen' not in memory:
4         memory['inventory_full_when_box_seen'] = 0
5         memory['box_encounters'] = 0
6         memory['description'] = "Percentage of times the
7             inventory was full when the box was encountered."
8
9     # Check if the box is in the observation
10    and the inventory is full
11    if observation['agent']['image'][3][5][0] == 7 and
12    len(observation['inv']) > 0:
13        memory['inventory_full_when_box_seen'] += 1
14    if observation['agent']['image'][3][5][0] == 7:
15        memory['box_encounters'] += 1
16
17    # Compute final result at the end of trajectory
18    if memory['box_encounters'] > 0:
19        memory['result'] = {"inventory_full_when_box_seen":
20            memory['inventory_full_when_box_seen'],
21            "box_encounters": memory['box_encounters']}
22    else:
23        memory['result'] = 0 # No box encounters
24
25    return memory
```